

WEBINAR: DIAMAS with CRAFT-OA and PALOMERA

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Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

On June 20, 2023, DIAMAS will take part in a webinar in collaboration with two other HORIZON Europe-funded projects: CRAFT-OA and PALOMERA.

June 20, 2023 - 1 p.m. CEST

[REGISTER HERE!](#)

The three projects work towards an equitable future for scholarly communication, with academic communities at the centre. The webinar will present this vision and introduce each project's area of focus. The discussion will demonstrate the projects' common goal for open and equitable scholarly publishing.

While DIAMAS focuses on developing common standards, guidelines and practices for the Diamond publishing sector, CRAFT-OA and PALOMERA have different aims. The former looks at the IT systems behind journal platforms to help them upscale, professionalise, and reach stronger interoperability. The latter, PALOMERA, is developing actionable recommendations and concrete resources to support and coordinate aligned funder and institutional policies for Open Access books.

In the session, DIAMAS will be placed in a broader context, displaying how we collaborate with other actors in the Open Access space and plan for long-term impact in the advancement of community-led publishing.

Participants will have the chance to engage with the three projects and their vision for community-driven open scholarly publishing.

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Register for this webinar to be part of this conversation and help us shape the future of Open Access as a community!

For additional details and registration:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZcqf-morT4jGNa5L7laZv5TOLGu4Z1Czi4>

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